

Figure S5. Expression of neddylation-related proteins

Proteome analysis of serum samples was performed using four biological replicates for the OFC-positive group and five biological replicates for the OFC-negative group. Proteins related to neddylation were labeled on volcano plots (A) 1 h after OFC, (B) 2 h after OFC, (C) at symptom onset in the OFC-positive group, (D) 1 h after OFC, and (E) 2 h after OFC in the OFC-negative group. Proteome analysis of serum samples was performed using four biological replicates for the OFC-positive group and five biological replicates for the OFC-negative group.